

USE OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article discusses the use of idioms in the English language.*

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Thematic group of acquisitions English acquisitions are in lexical-semantic relations such as synonymy and antonymy, and together with the members of certain paradigms, they are combined into thematic groups. Such thematic groups have their place in the language based on hierarchical (level) relations. As the vocabulary of the language develops in accordance with the changes in society, the place of native words plays a primary role in the enrichment of the lexicon.

After independence, the direct assimilation of borrowed words into our language increased. In particular, English acquisitions are of great importance. English words that have been acquired in our language can be studied by dividing them into social-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports thematic groups. English acquisitions related to the thematic group of the sports field have been acquired so much after independence that it is convenient and appropriate to separate them from the words of the cultural and educational field and study them in a systematic way. Currently, most of these words are actively used in oral and written speech as modern

layer words. English acquisitions can be studied by classifying them on the basis of the following thematic groups:

1. lexicon of the thematic group related to the socio-political sphere;
2. lexicon of the thematic group related to the economic sphere;
3. lexicon of the thematic group related to the cultural and educational sphere;
4. lexicon of the thematic group related to the field of sports.

Today, many of the words recorded in our dictionaries are still used in the press pages. In particular, many lexemes used in the field of information technology do not have recommended variants in Uzbek dictionaries. In our opinion, if necessary, they should be Uzbekized in accordance with the nature of our language and included in our dictionaries. we learn by classifying based on.

Food name: steak, hamburger, yogurt, cake, ketchup, jam, etc.

Drink names: cocktail, Coca-Cola, Pepsi-Cola, pom, whiskey, etc.

Names of clothing: sweater, jeans, cowgirl, jacket, pajamas, sweater, panties, raglan, etc.

Name of household appliances: mixer, player/player etc.

Cosmetics and household items: styling, shampoo, hair dryer, services, etc.

Names implying the concept of place: station, arboretum, drainage, square, camping, club, college, cottage, motel, bar (small restaurant, tavern), tunnel, zoo, hall park, supermarket, etc.

Fabric names: belting, teak, reps, sheviot, nylon, covercoat, etc.

Name of transport vehicles: trolleybus, express, tram, pickup, liner, trailer, tanker, etc.

Scientific terminology:

Fields of science, names of directions: logistics, ufology, management, etc.

Terms of worldview, theory and socio-political field: formalism, centrism, trade unionism, dominion, impeachment, lockout, summit, centrist, laborist, leader, rally, speaker, charter, boycott, etc.

Regarding the economic sphere and trade: leasing, export, banknote, broker, warrant, voucher, grant, dumping, dealer, discount, import, importer, investor, barter, budget, marketing, manager, holding, clearing, consulting, bartender, businessman, business, etc.

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